

**GENERAL TRENDS TOWARDS SAVING LANGUAGE RESOURCES
AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE WORD FORMATION OF MODERN
ENGLISH SLANG**

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Annotation The main manifestation of language economy in English slang is the reduction. The flourishing of sciences, their great accessibility and a huge number of discoveries that dramatically changed the world in the XX-XXI centuries, gave rise to a sharp increase in the number of four main types of abbreviations that originated initially in the professional slang of participants in various fields of activity.

Key words: manifestation, reduction, utterance, formation, language level, deviation, lexical content, abbreviation, truncations, slang, language economy.

Both language and slang have constantly developed and are developing new, more progressive, often unified language tools for the design of language information. This is equally inherent in both morphology and syntax, and word formation, and word formation at the level of speech has, due to functional features, a number of specific features. Thus, the emotionality of an utterance can be realized in a word-formation way when using colloquially-colored word-formation means with greater expressiveness; ease finds its own the expression, for example, in the use of such word-formation models, which are either completely not represented in other styles of language, or the lexical content of which represents a deviation from the generally accepted norms of word formation at the language level, the desire for humor, ridicule and satire, is expressed in the use of words, both of a low-productive and occasional nature. Conciseness, the desire to save language means lead to the use of various kinds of abbreviations, truncations, contamination, etc., which are implemented on the basis of the definition.

The main manifestation of language economy in English slang is the reduction. The flourishing of sciences, their great accessibility and a huge number of discoveries that dramatically changed the world in the XX-XXI centuries, gave rise to a sharp increase in the number of four main types of abbreviations that originated initially in the professional slang of participants in various fields of activity. Having passed the "run-in" in the professional environment, a significant number of these lexical units made their way into the sphere of wider use and became the property of various speech styles

Four main types of formations are presented:

1. truncation (39% of the total number of neologisms).

Among them, the absolute majority are apocopic (by truncating the final part of the lexical unit), for example, gene (adj) = genetic; lib (n) = liberation; promo (n) = promotion

The initial abbreviation is extremely poorly represented, for example : copter (n) = helicopter

Activation of the "paired" truncation of phrases (only of the apocopic type) is also noted, for example: hi-tec (adj, n) = High-Technology;

hi-fi (adj, n) = High Fidelity; haz-chem (n, adj) = Hazardous Chemicals;

lo-cal (adj, n) = Low Calorie

2. acronyms (27% of the total number of neologisms) pronounced as full words, for example: : AIDS – acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome;

ALGOL = algorithmic language; ECU – European Currency Unit/

Interestingly, there is often a deliberate "fitting" of a neoplasm in the form of an already existing word in order to attract attention or as a result of striving for originality, for example: : start –Strategic Arms Reduction Talks, ASH – Action On Smoking To Health; NOW – National Organization For Women

- 3.abbreviations (19%) of the total number of neologisms)

The analysis shows that technical terms, names of organizations, enterprises and associations of various kinds are most often abbreviated.

There are two-component ones, for example: EC – European Community;

FM – Frequency Modifier;

Three-component, for example: ABM – Anti-Ballistic Vissiles; EFL -English as a Foreign Language

Four- and more component: ALCM – Anti-Launched Cruise Missile;

NEDS – National Economic Development Council.

4. mixed-type formants (15% of the total), somehow:

- with abbreviations – with an abbreviation of the initial component of a complex word or phrase, as, for example, in widely known E-mail, E-number, (E = Electronic);

- with the reduction of the final component, for example: Big C (abbr. For “Cancer”);

- with the connecting element “&”, for example: S&M = Sadism and Masochism

- with a "/" sign, for example: AC/DC;

- combined alphanumeric type, as in : UB40 = Unemployment Benefit Form 40; MI6 = Military Investigation department 6.

The next in productivity and manifestation to the economy of language resources is conversion. Just as in the word formation of the literary standard, in professional slang the most productive is the model according to which a large number of verbs are formed from "instrument" to "action" (N – V), for example: to telex, to xerox, to source, to softdock, to doorstep.

The formation of nouns from verbs is slightly less productive, which is probably due to the fact that in English nouns are easily (and more "habitually") formed from verbs by affixation, and the increase in valence abilities and the expansion of the field of word–formation meanings of the main suffix in this model - er is more significant than ever.

Being one of the most productive suffixes in all layers of the English language of the national period, at present this suffix carries out word formation according to the models characteristic of the literary standard:

- V + -er = N e.g. work – worker; poke – poker;
- N + -er = N London– Londoner; hat – hatter; Geography –geographer

So, by expanding its valence abilities, it can join any basis, simple or complex, any part of speech, different types of phrases, and, unlike the literary standard, where the suffix –er has a "purely" agentive-instrumental meaning, it becomes more universal in slang, while derivative words have a single semantic basis. "correlations" with the concept that the producing basis denoted.

As studies show, the suffix -er can be joined

- to the basis of the participle II of irregular verbs:

gone – goner = ‘a broken person’ ;

taught – taughter – everlasting student

- not only to the verb proper, but also to the postposition, with the formation of complex words like: cutter-offer; goer-awayer; adder-upper;

- to the suggested phrases: goer-to-bedder; putter-to-ender; reader-in bedder;

- to adjectives: fresh fresher; green- greener; dead – deader; lone – loner;

- to superlatives of adjectives (however, only suppletive type): best – bester; worst – worster;

- to the basics of numerals: one – oner; two – twoer; fi ve – fi ver; ten – tenner; fi rst – fi rster; second – seconder;

- to adverbs and words of the status category: : once – oncer; twice – twicer; alone – aloner;

- to acronyms: SOL – soler; SOP – soper

All of the above justifies the low productivity of the V – N conversion model, but, on the other hand, illustrates the manifestation of the trend towards unification and economy of linguistic means in modern English word formation.

However, let's return to modern conversion models. Among the conformable lexical units, there is a noticeably greater number of verbs with postpositions, for example: turn-off = 'anything seen as unpleasant' ; sell-by = ' a date, stamped on goods time to be sold or consumed'; rep-off = ' a fraud, a swindle'; put-down = ' a verbal attack, a snub'.

The Adj – N model practically does not lag behind in the number of neoplasms , for example: nasties = 'unpleasant circumstances'; wrinkly = 'an agein person'

However, the largest number of nouns are formed from adjectives ending in – ic and – al, for example: acrylic, casual, transuranic and e.t.c

The tendency to economy is also widely manifested in the formation of complex nouns of an attributive nature in general, but in which the attributive dependence has a completely different character than in the determinative compound words of the neutral layer of vocabulary. These include words whose semantic content cannot be identified from the semantics of their direct components, since it can only be obtained by attracting additional lexical means that consisted outside the structure of this type of complex word. New lexical units constructed according to this model are characterized by a more capacious semantic content, otherwise it can to be implemented through a more cumbersome structure in lexical and syntactic terms. The compactness, expression and novelty of the lexical unit form serve in the word formation of modern slang as an effective means of compression with maximum information transfer.

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